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कला, मानविकी एवं वाणिज्य की मानक शोध पत्रिका

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दिनांक 10, 11 व 12 दिसम्बर 2022

National Education Policy-2020 (Challenges and Prospects)

राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति - 2020 (चुनौतियाँ और सम्भावनाएँ)

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Mr. Mahesh Kumar Bawwa

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प्रधान संपादक

डॉ. अश्विनी महाजन

दिल्ली विश्वविद्यालय, दिल्ली

संपादक

प्रो. प्रमून दत्त सिंह

महात्मा गांधी केन्द्रीय विश्वविद्यालय, मोतिहारी

डॉ. फूल चन्द

दिल्ली विश्वविद्यालय, दिल्ली

संजय शिक्षक प्रशिक्षण महाविद्यालय, जयपुर

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दृष्टिकोण

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नोट: पत्रिका में प्रकाशित लेखकों के विचार अपने हैं। उसके लिए पत्रिका/संपादक/संपादक मंडल को उत्तरदायी नहीं ठहराया जा सकता। पत्रिका से सम्बंधित किसी भी विवाद के निपटारे के लिए न्याय क्षेत्र दिल्ली होगा।

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National Education Policy 2020: A Viewpoint on the Implementing Challenges in Hospitality and Tourism Education System of India

Mahesh Kumar Bairwa

*Lecturer, State Institute of Hotel Management, Jodhpur (Rajasthan), India 342001
(Affiliated to NCHMCT, MOT, GOI Noida, UP)*

Dr. Vipula Mathur

*Associate Professor, Rajdhani Engineering College, Jaipur Affiliated to RTU (Rajasthan Technical
University, Kota) Jaipur (Rajasthan)*

Abstract

India ratified Goal 4 of the UN's Agenda for Sustainable Development in 2015, which states that all people should have access to high-quality education and opportunities for lifelong learning. In order to achieve the intended sustainable aim, the Indian government introduced the New Education Policy (NEP) in 2020 because the current educational system was insufficient. This investigation seeks to assess the NEP paradigm in the higher education sector as an inclusive educational policy that places an emphasis on building knowledge and value based education. Authors seek to peek deep in to the policy documentation and its implementation in the education system of hospitality & tourism education system of Indian universities and other institutions and tries to analyze and asses its various parameter in consideration with hospitality and tourism education. NEP 2020 is anticipated to significantly improve India's higher education system. The goal is to build India 2.0 for the twenty-first century, which will undoubtedly assume a leadership position on the world stage. The majority of NEP 2020 is a fairly forward-thinking text, with a clear understanding of the existing socio-economic landscape and the potential to tackle future difficulties. By 2030, India might become a hub for education especially in the field of hospitality and tourism education on a global scale if successfully executed. However challenges are need to address by the education system stakeholders with immediate approach.

Keywords: National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020), Hospitality and Tourism Education, Hotel Industry, Indian Education System

Introduction

Countries improve their educational institutions to enhance societal advancement (Rizvi & Lingard, 2009). To promote inclusive and equitable educational system in the country, India's Government (GoI) devised the National Policy on Education (NPE) in 2020 (Kaurav, Suresh, Narula, & Baber, 2020). Many universities are planning to implement the new education policy and many are in process to assess the resources, infrastructures and other requirement at par with regulations of NEP 2020. Although, many institutions are creating awareness among the education stakeholders about the policy, its benefits and challenges if any through open discussions, talks and conferences etc. Various scholars have stressed their ideas and thoughts over the different education levels of schooling, HEI (Higher Education Institution) and other courses. The most of the studies are over the generalized courses of medical, engineering, management and other humanities courses. This research article tries to provide the glimpses of National Education Policy 2020 in reference to hospitality and tourism education in the country with the following research questions in the form of view point generated from the secondary resources.

- To understand the NEP 2020 in reference to earlier existing education policies of the nation.
- To assess the implacability of NEP 2020 in the education system of Hospitality and Tourism of the country.
- To assess the major prospects and challenges faced by the hospitality and tourism education industry in respect to NEP 2020.

Hospitality and Tourism Education System

There are various significances of tourism and hospitality education in the country such as economic, infrastructural, capacity building, employment, Youth and nation-building, and international and inter-state understanding and peace etc. The National Action Plan for Tourism, unveiled in May 1992, encouraged the development of tourism education in India. In India hospitality and tourism education is primarily being provided through various institutions under the umbrella of NCHMCT (National Council for Hotel Management and Catering Technology, Society). NCHMCT was set up in the year 1982 by the Government of India as an autonomous body for coordinating growth and development of hospitality education in the country (Bairwa, & Kumari, 2020). Under the Ministry: IITMs were started to provide human resource in travel and tourism sector where as IHMs were created to cater the skilled professional graduate in the field of catering and hotels (Bairwa, & Kumari, 2020). The first IHM was established in 1954 in Mumbai (Maharashtra). Currently 71 IHMs are in operation, all over the India: 21 Central IHMs, 25 SIHMs, 14 Food Craft Institute (FCI), 1 Public Sector Undertaking (PSU) and 24 Private Institute of Hotel Management (nchmct.nic.in, 2022). Along with these institution, universities (private and Government) are also imparting H&T education in the country. However, their curriculum, credit scheme are not same. Some institutions are operating under the umbrella of AICTE (All India Council for Technical Education), State Board of Technical Education, even some universities is covered under UGC (Union Grant Commission), and they are self eligible for implementing their own curriculum and awarding degrees. From these institution and universities every year more than one lakh students completes their studies and serve to the country through various employment opportunities (hospitality.com).

Historical Evolution of Education Policies in India

In the past, information dissemination and education delivery have a long and illustrious history in India. At least 15 universities or institutions of higher learning are known to have existed in ancient India, including Takshashila, Nalanda, and Mithila, to name a few. They crumbled and were totally destroyed under the relentless assaults of savage invaders and attackers. The "Gurukul" institution preserved the rich ethos of teachings and customs, nonetheless. The new age of English-dominant university setup under the British Empire came into being. Especially under Lord Macaulay's misguided ideas and his self-serving plans to produce generations of bureaucrats and clerical workers who would slavishly and obediently serve the British Raj's rulers. There was established and maintained a system of servitude and mediocrity. Scholarly principles, creative thinking, and a critical analytical mindset were scorned and mercilessly suppressed. The historic, cultural, and legitimately indigenous philosophy was suppressed and replaced by succeeding administrators, who advanced this mindset/plan and artificially transplanted this system.

After India gained its independence in 1947, a commission led by Dr. S. Radhakrishnan, the country's second president and one of the greatest educators (Teacher's Day is observed his birth anniversary), attempted to update previous policies and bring them into line with the needs of the present and the future. The Kothari Commission in 1966, the National Education Policy in 1968 and then in 1986, which was modified in 1992 (1986/92), the Yashpal Committee in 1993, the National Knowledge Commission in 2006, the Tandon Committee in 2009, and the third NEP in 2019 were significant turning points in the development of educational reforms in India to shape the policies in correlation with the evolving challenges. And it has been introduced by Prime Minister Sh. Narendra Modi led NDA government in the name of "National Education Policy 2020" (NEP 2020) and got approved on 29 July 2020 in the parliament (education.gov.in/).

National Education Policy 2020

This NEP 2020, introduced in the verge of giving universal acknowledge to the importance of good quality and universal education in the overall well-being of the economy and society. As per Praveen Jha and Puja Parvati (2020) "it is a truism that governments need to be committed and proactive in ensuring relevant, robust policy frameworks and their adequate provisioning".

There are mainly four parts, the first three being various levels of learning followed by the actual implementation. Two parts are discussed in this to conceptualize the scope in higher education.

Part I – School education, Part II – Higher education, Part III – Other key areas of focus and Part IV – Making it happen (implementation).

Part I – School education, the model of may be understood with the given diagram-1, comparing with existing education model at present.

Figure 1: Diagrammatic representation of existing and proposed (Source: NEP2020, Gov.in)

The present day 10+2 structure of school curricula is to be replaced by a 5+3+3+4 (total of 15 years) curricular structure corresponding to ages 3–8 (5) + 8–11 (3) + 11–14 (3) + 14–18 (4) years, respectively. This will bring the up until now, uncovered group of age group of 3–6 years under school curriculum, globally accepted as the crucial stage of mental faculty development, early childhood care education, pedagogical framework for experiential learning, attaining foundational literacy and numeracy, flexibility in choice of the subjects, no rigid boundary or separation between streams and curricular & extracurricular activities and overall development of the child through multilingualism and power of languages. Furthermore it also advocates for reforms in assessment, equitable and inclusive education, entrance test, teacher recruitment and career path etc.

Part II - Higher Education: The Higher Education Commission of India (HECI), a single regulator for HEIs in India, would consolidate several higher education (HE) regulatory bodies. A strong National Certification Council (NAC) will be established in place of the existing certification organizations (NAAC and NBA). The research and innovation financing in higher education would be supported by National Research Foundation (NRF). NEP has legislated for multidisciplinary education paradigm for higher educational institutions. These universities ought to have a campus with at least 3000 students. They have a 2030 target to become multidisciplinary, and by 2040, they hope to have 3000 students enrolled. Furthermore, these multidisciplinary universities can specialize in one of them and should either concentrate on research or teaching.

Figure 2, National Education Policy: Frame work for Higher Education

The colleges have the choice of becoming independent and issuing their own degrees or joining an already-existing university. The NEP discusses strategies for boosting student enrollment in various kinds of educational institutions. The current education policy places a special emphasis on GER (Gross Enrollment Ratio) because it is an issue of concern in India. The NEP places a strong emphasis on a multidisciplinary, holistic approach to education, and it only encourages research at the UG level nowadays. Current policies place a strong emphasis on a student's whole development through cross-disciplinary, outcome-based education. An academic bank of credit is being proposed at the national level to offer flexibility in degree acquisition and different entry-exit options at all levels of education.

To promote online learning and the digitization of libraries, a number of digital platforms will either be launched or refurbished (NEP, 2020). A student-focused teaching and learning approach will be used in place of the current teacher-focused teaching paradigm. Competency-based evaluation will replace the current Choice-based evaluation methodology. A continuous assessment approach will replace the end-of-semester examination model for evaluation and assessment. The focus will be on skill education for all HEIs. Additionally, they must provide counseling centers with counselors to look after the students' mental health. Since it will now be driven by the market, traditional education is undergoing a significant transition.

The Indian government wants to build top-notch educational institutions and draw in many foreign students. Additionally, a student's coursework from overseas universities would be awarded credit and treated equally in India. This will give students the option to begin a degree programme overseas and finish it in India (NEP, 2020 and Aithal & Aithal, (2020).

Scope for Private Institutions it is suggested that all private universities receive varying degrees of autonomy. Their accreditation, involvement in cutting-edge research, and provision of high-quality education will serve as the foundation for this autonomy. Additionally, they would have to maintain open financial transactions. Financial irregularities shouldn't exist, and a set method needs to be in place to monitor that. Private higher education institutions must offer free tuition and scholarships to deserving and meritorious students in every course. A mechanism has been established to monitor this during the accreditation process. When allocating research funds, which need to be completely based on the quality of the proposals, there shouldn't be any distinction between public and private institutions. However, Private HEIs need to have strength of more than 3000 student otherwise; they would be asked to close down (NEP, 2020) Aithal & Aithal, (2020).

NEP 2020 Implementation

Fourth part of the NEP 2020 policy document guide upon the implementation of the policy. Policy gives some framework of implementation, but looking to the hospitality and tourism education, it seems bit tricky. Although, for implementing any policy some authors has stated their views. As per Hess (2013), there is a distinction between enacting a policy or strategy and having it become standard operating procedure for educators, school leaders, and local communities. Administrations and educators may be left to work out the specifics of implementation, ultimately stopping the reform movement in its tracks (Hess, 2013). The implementation may pose some challenges like coordination issues, inadequacy of organizational resources, reaction of organization against reforms. However, education stakeholders are increasingly diverse and growing in pace with international bodies and institution with the thought of global villages with diverse functionalities. In this course, the use of technology may contribute helping role as well as acting agencies may perform their duties in the corrective implementation.

Prospects & Challenges of NEP 2020 in Hospitality and Tourism Education - As discussed earlier, hospitality and tourism studies are started late in the country after independence. Mostly the education is imparted by institute affiliated with NCHMCT (National Council for Hotel Management and Catering Technology), an apex body for developing human resources for hotels and tourism industry enterprises working as an autonomous body under Ministry of Tourism Govt. of India. As NEP 2020 proposes, the introduction of four year multidisciplinary undergraduate program with multiple exit options i.e. exit after one year with a certificate or after two years with diploma or after three/four years with a bachelors degree. This policy seems most desirable policy for the hospitality institutes as the present system of education does not allow the peers to exit in between the programs. Presently NCHMCT offering three years program of B.Sc. in Hospitality and Hotel Administration (in Collaboration with IGNOU university), where selection is made through the competition test conducted by NTA (National Testing Agency) and students gets enrolled in the NCHM affiliated institutes (Central Govt., State Govt. and Private institutes affiliated with NCHM). In the existing systems, institute also offers the one and half year diploma in core trades of hotel operations viz. Front Office, Food & Beverage Production and services, Housekeeping and Bakery and Confectionery. Also some institute offers Master of Science (Two years full time program), PG diploma in Front office and Accommodation Management, Craft Courses for providing entry level operational manpower to the industry. All the courses are separate in their credit system.

After the proposed implementation of NEP 2020, peers will get an opportunity to exit from the course and awarding of the diploma or certificates shall be done. In the present systems of education, there is no provision of credit transfer

from one course to another and even lateral entry systems is not there. Moreover, four years degree with research component will make the students ready for academics, where they can directly pursue Ph.D., as they will be equipped with prior research knowledge. As Gartner (2019), states that, "More than 50% of higher education institutions will begin redesigning their student experience with the goal of making it more integrated and personalized by 2021, making technology a critical element to achieve this objective". So, the technological embedded curriculums and tie-ups with foreign universities may be done to bring excellence in the education at par with global academics. After have a glimpse over the prospects of NEP2020, it imposes some challenges also to the existing system of education. Some of the major challenges in overall and some particularly given for the hospitality and tourism industry are discussed below:

1. As it can be seen from the formulation, it appears to be designed to encourage the privatization of education in India. (NEP, 2020). The document also mentions that among other things, encouraging the top 100 foreign universities to open their doors to India. It is arguable whether this serves to promote profiteering or the cause of education.
2. Despite the fact that NEP 2020 emphasizes the need for increased transparency, particularly in relation to pricing structure. It provides no guidance on how to address the escalating capitation epidemic private colleges, many of which are controlled by strong political and religious organizations, charge tuition. Thus, universal education will always remain a pipe dream (Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S., 2020)
3. NEP 2020, mention that students until 5th class should be taught in mother tongue or regional language, however, hospitality and tourism education gives more emphasis on English as plays an instrumental role to connect with the outer world of hospitality industry.
4. As per the policy document, a new target of 50% GER (Gross Enrollment Ratio) seems an ambitious figure to aim by 2035 especially in the hospitality and tourism education sector.
5. NEP 2020, places a strong emphasis on cognitive abilities, learning results, and quality studies. It also places restrictions on institutional autonomy and weak regulatory and governance frameworks, which result in low Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). Most students are discouraged from pursuing higher education as a result of these crippling flaws; the Total Enrolment Ratio (GER) in higher education is a meagre 26% compared to 58% in Senior Secondary and 79% in Secondary. The NEP aims to remedy this by emphasizing adaptability, multidisciplinary, capability development, and high-quality research. The national and state governments must collaborate to ensure that the commitments do not become meaningless platitudes because education is a parallel theme of the list.
6. At present hospitality education in India is governed by Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India as an umbrella for NCHMCT, where amalgamation of all institution without a proper framework seems uneasy task for the education stakeholders. Further, Institutional governance bodies like UGC and AICTE shall be amalgamated in Higher Education Commission of India (HECI), this may cover the entire university affiliated bodies but the question mark still lies on NCHM affiliated autonomous bodies.

Conclusion

Higher education in India is to be modernized as part of NEP 2020. It will make use of worldwide communities' cooperation and their experiences. In addition, ICT would be used in higher education delivered in Indian universities and colleges under NEP 2020 to meet modern educational needs. Keeping up with the outmoded educational system is pointless now. The Indian government will need to make significant adjustments to the higher education curricula to meet the demand for qualified workers around the world. NEP 2020 implementation would be extremely difficult as a result. The policy will undoubtedly bring about new and revolutionary developments.

From the current system of several regulators, higher educational institutions (HEI) will fall under the purview of one regulator. There will be a free-wheeling, autonomous atmosphere to support academic independence, research breadth, and an emphasis on innovation. Foreign universities will have the chance to open campuses in India, and there won't be any obstacles standing in the way of Indian universities opening campuses abroad. As it offers students several entry and departure options and allows them to continue their higher education after taking a break for job, NEP 2020 will significantly boost India's talent development. Overall, NEP 2020 is a very forward-thinking text with a solid understanding of the socioeconomic environment now and the potential to address difficulties in the future.

However, on the other side of coin, especially in the field of tourism and hospitality, the governing bodies at present, seems passive, and not formulated any initiation step so far. As the biggest problems seem that, institution affiliated with NCHMCT (under MOT, GOI) does come under UGC and AICTE, neither with their affiliation nor under their control. Also, all the institution, presently affiliated with NCHMCT, they have their own autonomy for their operation, governance under different rules and regulation of state. Furthermore, NCHM has collaboration with IGNOU (Indira Gandhi National Open University, Delhi) and awarding three years bachelor's degree to their peers. Which is contrary itself in the purview of the present education system, then getting reforms and resolution in the current education systems of hospitality and tourism education seem the nuts tough to crack.

Limitations and Further Study

This research article is presented the study in the viewpoint, generated from the secondary source of data available in the repository of quality indexed articles, NEP 2020 policy documents etc. This article has highlighted the theoretical construct only with the viewpoint. However, NEP 2020 is in initial phase of implementation, where preliminary requirements of implementation are at the outset. Authors are in position to extend the study with primary data to bring out the exact results with sentiments.

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